

The Quality of the Air we Breathe is Getting Worse, the Dust can be Dangerous: In what way?

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ABSTRACT: Based on the observation that air quality measuring devices have shown increased levels of dust pollution in recent years, we carried out an investigation over two years. This confirmed the assumption of increasing air pollution: a significant increase in the parts per million of dust particles. By analysing the filter contents of an air ionizer, we were able to find various pollutants: Arsenic, aluminum, titanium, fluorides, barium as well as mold spores. The causes can be assumed to be Geoen지니어ing, Solar Radiation Management and Stratospheric Aerosol Injection. Air purification devices are therefore becoming increasingly important.

KEY WORDS: air quality, air pollution, geoen지니어ing, stratospheric aerosols, air purification

INTRODUCTION

You can't normally see the dust in the air. However, when the sun shines in through a gap, you can see it and are amazed. The simplest method of assessment is to have an air purifier or air ionizer that includes a dust meter. It measures the parts per million (ppm) or ug/air volume by attenuating a light beam between the transmitter and receiver. This means that the air quality is visible at all times.

The most problematic are positively charged particles and molecules, as they have an electron deficit and therefore interact aggressively with the body as free radicals. This mainly affects inhalation, which is harmful to the airways, but also the skin, as charged particles settle on it. Instead of a pure filter device, which does not take into account the charge of the dust, an ionizer should be used, which removes positively charged dust from the air and adds negatively charged ions to the air instead.

The air ionizer (1) we use cleans and disinfects the air using three different, parallel methods: The internal UVC lamp eliminates viruses. The air ionization splits the air and dust molecules. The antibacterial filter eliminates all pathogens that were not eliminated by the two methods mentioned.

In earlier times, the dust from inside the home was mainly house dust, mite droppings, animal hair, etc. This has not changed much. Not much has changed in this respect; you could positively change the situation by ventilating and letting in "fresh air". It is more problematic when it comes to dust from outside. This has steadily increased in recent years, both quantitatively and qualitatively-aggressively. The difference is striking when there was a high-pressure area without rain: constantly rising dust levels; or when there was a low-pressure area with rain: falling dust levels. Rain obviously and understandably transports the dust down into the ground.

Test results

We carried out an investigation over two years. Over the period from mid-2022 to mid-2023 and from mid-2023 to mid-2024, the ppm value in an office room (42 m²) was read and recorded twice a day under three different conditions (table):

- A) Windows closed for > 2 hours,
- B) Tilted windows for > 1 hour,
- C) Open windows for > 1 hour.

The standard range specified by the manufacturer is 0 to 7 ppm. Note: one week in each period was excluded, namely when the so-called Sahara dust covered Europe and the values rose exorbitantly with the window open.

Table

Situation	Period	Mean value ppm	Stand.dev.	Significances	
A	2023	6.5	1.3	A v B 2023	**
	2024	7.3	1.4	A v B 2024	**
B	2023	9.6	2.3	A v C 2023	****

	2024	11,2	2.7	A v C 2024	*****
C	2023	11.9	3.1	B v C 2023	*
	2024	14.5	3.9	B v C 2024	**

DISCUSSION

The increase in dust in the air over time is clear. The problems are not indoors, but come in from outside. The age of "good, fresh air" is clearly over. Although it may still appear to be so, as it is predominantly cool, its cleanliness or purity must be described as increasingly inadequate. This raises questions about the causes and the effects.

We scraped the dust off the filters and had it analyzed in the laboratory. We found significantly elevated levels of arsenic, aluminum, titanium, barium and fluoride. When incorporated, these substances e.g. pollute people's pineal glands. Mold spores were also detected penetrating into the lungs. Where do these substances of health concern come from?

It is no secret that geoengineering (2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9) involves the manipulation of the weather and the air. Geoengineering can be defined as a series of large-scale technical measures that intervene in the Earth's natural systems in order to combat climate change. These measures aim to slow down or reverse global warming, for example by reducing the amount of sunlight reaching the earth. This is esp. Solar Radiation Management (SRM) (10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20): It aims to reduce the amount of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface. Examples include releasing aerosols into the stratosphere to reflect sunlight or brightening clouds to reflect more sunlight back into space. Geoengineering is controversial because the long-term effects on the global climate and ecosystems are difficult to predict, and there are ethical concerns about the control of such technologies.

The "release of aerosols into the stratosphere" refers to a process in which small particles or droplets (aerosols) are introduced into the stratosphere, i.e. the upper part of the Earth's atmosphere. This could theoretically lead to a cooling of the Earth's surface and thus slow down the global rise in temperature. A well-known example of this effect is the eruption of the Pinatubo volcano in 1991, which released large quantities of sulphur dioxide into the stratosphere. This gas formed aerosols that combined with dust particles, reflected sunlight and lowered the global average temperature for several years. In geoengineering research, the release of aerosols into the stratosphere is being investigated as a possible method of artificially cooling the planet. This method is often referred to as "stratospheric aerosol injection" (SAI) (21,22,23). With SAI, for example, sulphur compounds could be injected into the stratosphere to achieve an effect similar to that of large volcanic eruptions, but also other reflective substances such as light metal particles, e.g. aluminum or titanium.

The release of aerosols into the stratosphere is highly controversial. Critics warn of the potential risks and undesirable side effects such as disruption to the weather, clouds, rain and air. In summary, the release of aerosols into the stratosphere refers to a climate protection measure that is, however, associated with considerable ethical and scientific problems.

One component of the SRM could be the chemtrails, they are what some call the white trails you see left behind as a plane passes overhead. Believers in the chemical aspect of chemtrails say those trails are actually clouds of chemicals used by the governments for a variety of purposes from opens in a new windowweather modification. The theories usually claim that normal jet plane output should dissipate quickly so any clouds that do not disappear immediately must be full of additional, undisclosed substances.

The author often observes that in areas of the world with seas or low population density, the sky is equally blue in the morning and evening, whereas in densely populated areas such as Central Europe it is still blue at 07.00, but from late morning onwards it looks as shown in the illustration: a milky veil. Chemtrails persist and confluent. Solar radiation should obviously be reduced, but this can have negative consequences for nature as a whole.

Illustration: Photo of the sky at 16.00 o'clock, Switzerland

CONCLUSIONS

Humans and nature have long been adapted to the sun, wind, rain and air. Whether climate change is predominantly man-made is open to debate. According to our findings, the greenhouse gas CO² is not the main factor in the warming of the atmosphere, but the effects of radiation. This concerns technical electromog, radioactivity released on the earth's surface and the components of stratospheric aerosol injections heated by the absorption of solar radiation, which gradually sink downwards according to the law of gravity. Before entering the ground as a result of rain, they end up in the air that people breathe.

The air pollution that we have been able to detect is a disease-causing factor that should no longer go unnoticed. As no one can be expected to wear a gas mask, the use of air purifiers has become essential. Keeping the windows open all the time can no longer be recommended, only short-term ventilation. The air in rooms with air purification systems has become the only clean air. Outside, the air we breathe is only acceptable during and after rain.

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